

Impact on Psychological Health of Nursing Students: Closure of College and Lockdown Due to Corona-virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)

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Abstract

There are severe effects of COVID-19 on physical and psychological health of people and especially vulnerable population such as children and old aged people. This study aim to Investigate the psychological health status of nursing students under the epidemic situation of new Corona virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), explore the influencing factors of nursing students' psychological health under the stress condition of epidemic situation, and provide the basis for adopting mental health education. **Materials and Methods:** This study adopted quantitative research approach with an online survey design done during May-June 2020. Nursing students were selected through a Google form (web-based) survey, involve 632 nursing students. The snowball sampling method and the convenient sampling method were used to investigate the nursing students from pan India. Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) score Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7-item (GAD-7) scale were used to collect the data. The descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the analysis. **Results:** Majority of students participated 319 (50.47%) were minimal depress on level of depression. 420 (66.46%) students were minimum anxious on level of anxiety. Among all demographic variables, nursing course, B.Sc. year of nursing, where have you been during lockdown, do you have any history of quarantine recently and any worry about being infected with COVID-19 are significant with the level of depression. In demographic variables, gender, B.Sc. year of nursing, where have you been during lockdown, any past or current history of having psychiatric illness, do you have any history of quarantine recently and any worry about being infected with COVID-19 are significant with the level of anxiety. **Conclusions:** The study data indicated that nursing students were minimal depressed and anxious but also showed that depression and anxiety related to various demographic variables. During this pandemic and changes due to pandemic need special attention care for young generation from teachers and parents.

Keywords: Impact on Psychological Health, Nursing Students, Closure of College, Lockdown, Corona-virus, COVID-19

Introduction

In the past years many endemics and pandemics outbreaks occurred such as SARS in 2003, the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) in 2012 and the outbreak of Ebola disease in West Africa in 2014, which caused significant losses to the lives and property of people around the world. It has also caused serious trauma to people's mental health. Some studies have pointed out that the physical damage caused by these public health emergencies may be recovered within a short period of time, but the psychological impact will last for a long time . SARS epidemic in China in 2003 after the emergence of a large number of acute stress disorder, patients with diseases such as post-traumatic stress disorder, therefore, to the public as soon as possible the implementation of psychological crisis intervention is necessary .(1,2) December 2019, the new corona virus pneumonia (COVID-19) for the first time and quickly spread to 24 countries, national and global in Wuhan City, Hubei Province. The World Health Organization declared it as international emergency on January 30, 2020. COVID-19 infection is sudden, with extensive dissemination, lack of specific drugs, and life-threatening if not treated in time. In addition, the overload of epidemic information has a huge impact and impact on public psychology, causing them to feel panic, anxiety, worry, and depression. In order to stop the spread of the COVID-19 epidemic to the educational institute's campus, the Govt. of India and Ministry of Education decided to close all educational institute across the India and instructed to start online education. For college students, vacations are extended and long-term leaves are given to stay in their homes. Due to this uncertainty and long leaves students started having anxiety and depression. The current research on COVID-19 is focused on epidemiology and clinical research, and there is no research on college students 'mental health. This study aim to investigate the psychological health status of nursing students under the epidemic situation of new Corona virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), explore the influencing factors of nursing students' psychological health under the stress condition of epidemic situation, and provide the basis for adopting mental health education. The impact will provide accurate reference for relevant government departments and universities to the mental health education of nursing college students.

Need for the study

As COVID-19 cases increased suddenly all over the world, universities, colleges, schools cancelled or postponed all the teaching activities, events, sports, academic activities such as

conferences/workshops for a time period which does not had a plan of definite time. All activities cancelled which need physical meetings, instead of this all meetings, classes, workshops, and conferences started on online platform like Zoom, Google meet etc.

It was the time when teaching faculties, students and management of teaching institutes started to adjust which this sudden change of learning method which was not planned in advance. Teaching faculty encouraged students to adept this new normal method of teaching but at the same time they were also felt many difficulties like active interaction with students, discipline and evaluation of students. At the same time students were more uncomfortable and stressed due to sudden change in their teaching and learning methods. There were no training program or instruction to prepare for this change. It had impacted on student's psychological and physical health. Students were concerned and feared that this pandemic may affect their exam performance and future progress in studies. These psychological factors may hamper student's physical and mental health, so its require to identify factors affecting psychological domine of the students. Jinghui CHANG , Yuxin YUAN , Wang Dong conducted a study to find out the psychological health of college students under the COVID-19 pandemic, and influencing factors which affect mental health under the stress condition. A general questionnaire, self-compiled knowledge cognitive behavior table, generalized anxiety scale and depression symptom group scale were used to conduct an online questionnaire survey on 3881 Guangdong college students. In result they found that the incidence of anxiety was 26.60%, the incidences of mild 23.19%, moderate 2.71% and severe anxiety 0.70% respectively; the incidence of depression was 21.16 %, Including mild 16.98%, moderate 3.17%, and severe 1.01%. In Influencing factors they found out factors such as age, the higher level of awareness about COVID-19, more changed health behavior in the future. More than half of the students were prone to anxiety, and women, current suburbs, drinking history, and negative information in epidemic information accounted for more than half of them (P <0.05). (23)

Aim of the study

To investigate the psychological health status of nursing students under the epidemic situation of new Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), explore the influencing factors of nursing students' psychological health under the stress condition of epidemic situation, and provide the basis for adopting mental health education.

Materials and Methods An online survey was conducted among nursing students, data collection done between May to June 2020 from pan India. The study aim to assess level of

depressions and anxiety among students. An overall 632 samples enrolled and responded for the study. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional ethical committee wide letter no. AIIMS/Pat/IEC/2020/474. Data were collected after getting formal permission from the IEC. All participant in study signed informed consent after understanding the purpose of study. A self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection, Questionnaire consisted three sections: (a) demographics data (b) Questionnaire to measure the level of depression was the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9); (c) Questionnaire to measure the level of anxiety was, the Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7-item (GAD-7). Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the analysis of data.

Results

In demographic variable majority of nursing students were female 552 (87.34%), whereas 80 (12.66%) were male. The highest percentage 99.05% (626) were in the age group of 17-29 years whereas 0.79% (05) were in the age group of 30-42 and 0.16% (01) of nursing students were in the age group of 43-55. The maximum number of participants were pursuing 508 (80.38%) B.Sc. nursing whereas 112 (17.72%) were GNM and 12 (1.90%) were M.Sc. nursing. As per distribution of nursing students according to their year of GNM nursing of shows that the highest percentage 7.28% (46) were in the 1st year whereas around equal to 6.01% (38) were in 3rd year and 4.43% (28) of nursing students were in 2nd year GNM. Nursing students according to their year of B.Sc. nursing of shows that the highest percentage 25.16% (159) were in the 2nd year whereas around equal to 21.52% (136) were in 4th year, 20.25% (128) were in 3ed year and 13.45% (85) of nursing students were in 1st year. Distribution of nursing students according to their year of M.Sc. nursing of shows that 0.95% (6) were in the 2nd year whereas 0.95% (6) were in 1st year. Percentage wise distribution of nursing students according to residence during lockdown of shows that the majorities 83.23% (526) students were in home with family whereas 16.77% (106) students were in hostel. Percentage wise distribution of nursing students according to type of family of shows that the majorities 76.27% (150) students were from nuclear family whereas 23.73% (150) students were from joint family. Percentage wise distribution of nursing students according to responses of history of psychiatric illness of shows that the majorities 97.78% (618) students had no history of psychiatric illness whereas 2.22% (14) students had psychiatric illness. Percentage wise distribution of nursing students according to quarantine history of shows that the majorities 90.19% (570) students had no history of quarantine whereas 9.81% (62) students had history of quarantine. Percentage wise distribution of nursing students according

to worry regarding COVID-19 disease of shows that the majorities 53.16% (336) students were slightly worried or not worried whereas 27.53% (174) students were moderately worried and 19.30% (122) students were quite worried.

Figure. 1 Level of depression of nursing students.

Figure 1 explains level of depression among nursing students. The major findings are 319 (50.47%) of nursing students had minimal depression, the remaining 205 (32.44%) had mild depression, 80 (12.66%) had moderate depression, 25 (3.96%) had moderate to severe depression and 3 (0.47%) students had severe depression. The mean of the level of depression among nursing students is 5.30 with SD is 4.50.

Figure 2. Level of anxiety of nursing students

Figure 2 depicts level of anxiety among nursing students. The major findings are 420 (66.46%) of nursing students had minimal anxiety, the remaining 120 (18.99%) had mild anxiety, 63 (9.97%) had moderate anxiety, and 29 (4.59%) students had severe anxiety. The mean of the level of anxiety among nursing students is 4.42 with SD is 4.66

Table 1. Association between level of depression and selected demographic variables

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Demographic variables	Minimal	Mild	Moderate	Moderate to severe	severe	DF	X², P
1. Gender							
a) male	32	29	12	7	0	4	8.17, 0.08
b) female	287	176	68	18	3		
2. Age							
a) 17-29	316	203	79	25	3	8	0.89, 0.99
b) 30-42	2	2	1	0	0		
c) 43-55	1	0	0	0	0		
3. Nursing course							
a) B.Sc. Nursing	266	157	66	17	2	8	26.85, 0.0007
b) GNM	49	45	12	6	0		
c) M.Sc. Nursing	4	3	2	2	1		
4. GNM-Year of Nursing							
a) 1st Year	23	40	6	4	0	8	121.67, 0
b) 2nd Year	22	9	6	1	0		
c) 3rd Year	0	0	0	0	1		
5. B. Sc.-Year of Nursing							
a) 1st Year	24	54	5	2	0	12	29.13, 0.004
b) 2nd Year	44	88	23	4	0		
c) 3rd Year	81	72	9	6	0		
d) 4th Year	48	52	29	5	2		
6. M.Sc. Nursing-Year of Nursing Course							
a) 1st year	1	3	0	1	1	4	2.82, 0.58
b) 2nd year	2	1	2	1	0		
7. Where have you been during lockdown?							
a) In home with family	276	170	57	20	3	4	11, 0.026
b) In hostel	43	35	23	5	0		
8. Type of family							

a) Joint family	63	55	24	7	1	4	6.02, 0.19
b) Nuclear family	256	150	56	18	2		
9. Any past or current history of having psychiatric illness?							
a) No	314	201	76	24	3	4	3.91, 0.41
b) Yes	5	4	4	1	0		
10. Do you have any history of quarantine recently?							
a) No	272	194	79	23	2	4	21.91, 0.0002
b) Yes	47	11	1	2	1		
11. Any worry about being infected with COVID-19?							
a) Moderately worried	76	67	22	8	1	8	17.11, 0.028
b) Quite worried	50	43	20	8	1		
c) Slightly or not worried	193	95	38	9	1		

Table no.1 depicts that there is no significant association between the level of depression of nursing students and their gender, age, year of M.Sc. nursing, type of family, and responses of history of psychiatric illness.

Table reveals that there is a significant association between the level of depression of nursing students and their nursing course, year of GNM nursing, year of B.Sc. nursing, residence during lockdown, quarantine history, and worry regarding COVID 19 disease.

Table 2. Association between level of anxiety and selected demographic variables.

Demographic variables	Minimal	Mild	Moderate	Severe	DF	X ² , P
1. Gender					3	8.26, 0.04
a) male	47	13	13	7		
b) female	373	107	50	22		
2. Age						
a) 17-29	417	117	63	29	6	5.16, 0.52
b) 30-42	2	3	0	0		
c) 43-55	1	0	0	0		

3. Nursing course						
a) B.Sc. Nursing	338	90	53	27	6	9.06, 0.16
b) GNM	76	28	8	0		
c) M.Sc. Nursing	6	2	2	2		
4. GNM-Year of Nursing						
a) 1st Year	11	31	4	0	6	0.81, 0.99
b) 2nd Year	7	20	1	0		
c) 3rd Year	10	25	3	0		
5. B.Sc.-Year of Nursing						
a) 1st Year	18	60	5	2	9	41.19, 0
b) 2nd Year	21	114	12	12		
c) 3rd Year	17	99	8	4		
d) 4th Year	34	65	28	9		
6. M.Sc. Nursing-Year of Nursing Course						
a) 1st year	0	4	1	1	3	1.66, 0.79
b) 2nd year	2	2	1	1		
7. Where have you been during lockdown?						
a) In home with family	369	93	43	21	3	21.81, 0
b) In hostel	51	27	20	8		
8. Type of family						
a) Joint family	90	31	18	11	3	5.56, 0.13
b) Nuclear family	330	89	45	18		
9. Any past or current history of having psychiatric illness?						
a) No	412	118	62	26	3	9.31, 0.025
b) Yes	8	2	1	3		
10. Do you have any history of quarantine recently?						
a) No	368	117	57	28	3	11.71, 0.008
b) Yes	52	3	6	1		
11. Any worry about being infected with COVID-19?						
a) Moderately worried	96	47	20	11	6	27.27, 0.0001
b) Quite worried	71	30	14	7		
c) Slightly or not worried	253	43	29	11		

Table no.2 depicts that there is a significant association between the level of anxiety of nursing students and their gender, year of B.Sc. nursing, residence during lockdown, responses of history of psychiatric illness, quarantine history, and worry about being infected with COVID-19 disease.

Table reveals that there is no significant association between the level of anxiety of nursing students and their age, nursing course, year of GNM nursing, year of M.Sc. nursing, and type of family ($P > 0.05$).

Discussion

In the present study, most of the participant were females 87.34 (552), maximum participants 99.05 (626) were 17-29 years old. 69.47% of college students have a high level of recognition of COVID-19; the incidence of anxiety is 26.60%, of which the incidences of mild, moderate and severe anxiety are 23.19%, 2.71% and 0.70% respectively; the incidence of depression is 21.16 %, Including mild, moderate, moderate and severe 16.98%, 3.17%, 1.01%. The results of multi-factor analysis show that: the older you are, the higher your awareness of COVID-19, the more you will change your health behavior in the future, the less anxiety and depression your college students will receive. More than half of them are prone to anxiety, and women, current suburbs, drinking history, and negative information in epidemic information accounted for more than half of them ($P < 0.05$). (11) A study done to investigate the mental health status of college students under the new coronavirus pneumonia (COVID-19) epidemic, to explore the influencing factors of college students' mental health under the stress of the epidemic, and to provide a basis for adopting mental health education. Using the general situation questionnaire, self-compiled COVID-19 knowledge, cognition and behavior scale, generalized anxiety scale and depressive symptom cluster scale, a network questionnaire survey was conducted on 3881 Guangdong college students, and the unordered multi-class Logistic regression model was used for statistical analysis. 69.47% of college students have a high degree of awareness of COVID-19; the incidence of anxiety is 26.60%, of which the incidence of mild, moderate and severe anxiety are 23.19%, 2.71%, and 0.70% respectively; the incidence of depression is 21.16 %, including mild, moderate, moderately severe and severe 16.98%, 3.17% and 1.01%. (23) It can be seen that under the stress of the COVID-19 epidemic, the incidence of anxiety and depression among college students has increased significantly, and precise psychological intervention and health education measures are urgently needed. First of all, more attention should be paid to the College psychological

counselling centres should pay more attention to the psychological dynamics of female students and implement psychological intervention measures as soon as possible; College psychological counselling centres should provide remote psychological assistance to college students in need. Second, improving college students' awareness of COVID-19 is beneficial to college students' mental health. Finally, At this time, it is necessary to use the strength of family members, friends, and teachers to help college students get out of their negative emotions and face the difficulties brought by the epidemic with a positive attitude through more social support. At the same time, the government should release timely, open and authoritative information to improve the awareness rate of relevant knowledge of college students, reduce the psychological pressure of college students and improve their psychological coping ability. To sum up, relevant government departments and colleges and universities should strengthen monitoring and information management, take different health education measures according to the characteristics of college students in a timely manner, and carry out extensive and in-depth health education and health promotion activities (22) , so that college students can correctly understand COVID-19 19 related knowledge, improve self-protection awareness and ability, guide college students to adopt positive and healthy behaviors, and prevent them from being negatively affected by stress by helping each other.

Conclusion

Present pandemic caused many psychological issues in vulnerable population specially children and old aged people. So there was a need of a hour to find how this pandemic caused psychological conditions and factors which hamper children's mental health. The present study findings shows that majority of nursing students are depressed and anxious due to closer of universities/colleges, there level of depression and anxiety is associated with various demographic variables. Nursing course and year of nursing, residence during lockdown, quarantine history, and worry regarding COVID 19 disease are the areas of concern found in study for the depression management. Gender, year of nursing, residence during lockdown, responses of history of psychiatric illness, quarantine history, and worry about being infected with COVID-19 disease are the areas of concern found in study for management of anxiety. Universities and faculties should take care mental and psychological health of students during this pandemic time by educating and training programs. A specific structured training and counselling program for students to cope up with present pandemic and its effects should be plan. Universities and related departments should provide accurate mental health education for college students. There a need of further studies to find out how factors which impacted

children during pandemic spread time subsides as time pass and which have long term effect on children's psychological health.

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References

1. Chowell G, Abdirizak F, Lee S, et al. Transmission characteristics of MERS and SARS in the healthcare setting: a comparative study [J]. *BMC Med*, 2015, 13 (1): 210-22.
2. Kucharski AJ, Althaus CL. The role of superspreading in Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) transmission [J]. *Euro Surveill*, 2015, 20 (25): 14-8.
3. Breban R, Riou J, Fontanet A. Interhuman transmissibility of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus: estimation of pandemic risk [J]. *Lancet*, 2013, 382 (9893): 694-9.
4. Hu Junfeng, Hou Peisen. Contemporary health education and health promotion. Beijing: People's Medical Publishing House; 2005. p. 410.
5. Wu Yinxia, Wang Meijuan. Psychological intervention of post-traumatic stress disorder. *China Health Nutrition*, 2017, 27 (6): 87-8.
6. Lvqiu Yun, psychological thicket of SARS. Basic methods of intervention. *Chinese Journal of Mental Health*, 2003, 17 (8): 534-5.
7. Main A, Zhou Q, Ma Y, et al. Relations of SARS-related stressors and coping to Chinese college students' psychological adjustment during the 2003 Beijing SARS epidemic. *J Couns Psychol*, 2011, 58 (3): 410-23.
8. Hui DS, I Azhar E, Madani TA, et al. The continuing 2019- nCoV epidemic threat of novel coronaviruses to global health-The latest 2019 novel coronavirus outbreak in Wuhan, China. *Int J Infect Dis*, 2020, 93 (91): 264-6.

9. World Health Organization. Novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) situation report-17 [EB / OL] [2020.2.6]. "<https://www.who.int/docs/defaultsource/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20200206-sitrep-17-ncov.pdf?>
10. World Health Organization. Statement on the second meeting of the International Health Regulations (2005) Emergency Committee regarding the outbreak of novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) [EB / OL] [2020.1.30].
11. Nan Fang Yi Ke Da Xue Xue Bao . Analysis of mental health status and influencing factors of college students under the epidemic of new coronavirus pneumonia . Journal of Southern Medical University.2020 Feb 20; 40 (2): 171–176.)
12. Zhang Fengmei, Chen Jianwen, Xu Hengjian. Analysis of anxiety and depression of college students in a university in Shandong [J]. Modern Preventive Medicine, 2014, 41 (13): 2399-400, 2425.
13. Yang Xiulan, Jia Weihua, Xia Guo, et al. Analysis of the influence of social class background on college students 'depression and anxiety [J]. Chinese Journal of Disease Control, 2015, 19 (12): 1269-72.
14. 22. Tan Xiaodong. *Prevention and control of public health emergencies*. Wuhan: Hubei Provincial Health Publishing House; 2003. p. 45.
15. 23. Shelley E. *Taylor Health Psychology*. Beijing: People's Health Publishing House; 2006. pp. 167-9.
16. 24. Li Hong. *Health Psychology*. Wuhan: Wuhan University Press; 2007. pp. 305–17.
17. 25. Zhang Fengmei, Chen Jianwen, Xu Hengjian. Analysis of anxiety and depression of college students in a university in Shandong [J]. Modern Preventive Medicine, 2014, 41(13): 2399-400, 2425.
18. 26. Yang Xiulan, Jia Weihua, Xia Guo, et al. Analysis of the influence of social class background on college students' depression and anxiety [J]. Chinese Journal of Disease Control, 2015, 19(12): 1269 -72.
19. 27. Yi Ling, Wang Zhongcan, Jiang Zhikuan, et al. Research progress on psychological intervention in public health emergencies [J]. Chinese Journal of Public Health, 2010, 26(7): 929-30.
20. 28. Sun Zhongqing. Research on the Application of Positive Psychology in College Students' Mental Health Education. Journal of *Zaozhuang* University 2019;(3):131–5.
21. 29. Zhu Yonghua. An analysis of the mental health education path of college students under the new media environment [J]. Media Observation, 2016(5): 34-6

22. Pei Xuejin. Principles and strategies of three-dimensional integrated perspective construction in college students' mental health education [J]. Chinese School Health, 2015, 36(7): 1097-100.
23. Jinghui Chang, Yuxin Yuan, Dong Wang. Analysis of mental health status and influencing factors of college students under the epidemic of new coronavirus pneumonia [J]. Journal of Southern Medical University, 2020 Feb 20; 40 (2): 171-176.